

VALUING WHAT MATTERS IN URBAN CLIMATE GOVERNANCE

Co-Benefits Gaps and Functions in Making the Case for Action

JOEL TERWILLIGER | NET ZERO FUTURES BRIEF SERIES NO.2 OF 5

RESEARCH FOCUS AND POLICY CONTEXT

Co-benefits—social, health, economic, and resilience gains from climate action—have become central to the political and financial case for net zero. With \$4.5 trillion annually needed to reach global net zero by 2050, and 90% of that expected from private capital, cities are under structural pressure to prioritise a narrow subset of monetisable co-benefits. Voluntary reporting with no common methodology, competing frameworks, and severe capacity constraints compound this pressure—producing a system where carbon metrics dominate because they are required and standardised, while the co-benefits most critical for a just transition remain aspirational. Despite this, cities are not passive: they are actively developing co-benefits approaches in the absence of shared taxonomies, navigating the gap with limited resources and real ingenuity.

KEY FINDINGS

Co-benefits ambition progressively narrows in a four-stage cascade—from what frameworks propose, to what cities include in strategies, to what gets reported, to what is actually measured. Of 712 co-benefits identified across ten Mission cities' action plans, only 41% aligned with NetZeroCities Mission Platform impact framework indicators; most were activities or outputs, not impacts. At the cascade's end, analysis of 92 Mission cities' plans shows most co-benefits remain at the consideration level—without definitions, units of measure, or explicit monitoring. The Energy Access and Poverty Pillar (EAPP) case study shows even well-designed additions to reporting systems produce parallel, non-communicating data streams. These point to structural design issues, local contextual factors, and methodological and institutional gaps. The Four Functions Model—compliance, economies of scale, theories of change, and advocacy/communications—reveals how cities use co-benefits in climate governance and where gains can be made.

KEY MESSAGES FOR POLICY AND PRACTICE

- **Audit co-benefits in governance practice using the 4 Functions Model.** If urban governance work is dominated by compliance and advocacy/communications, there is a theories-of-change gap. Closing it means building participatory feedback loops with citizens—and establishing shared monitoring ownership across action planning, investment planning, and reporting teams.
- **Establish a minimum set of required co-benefits indicators.** Particularly for just transition and governance process outcomes, required reporting would enhance the evidence base available to all actors. A shared minimum taxonomy—drawing on the EU and UK taxonomies and where existing C40, NZC, and CDP frameworks already converge—would reduce city burden while enabling meaningful comparison and methodological progress.
- **Co-refine frameworks around what cities actually find useful.** The gap between comprehensive indicator frameworks and city uptake is a design problem. A systematic review of which co-benefits approaches cities are actually applying—and building that into framework refinement—would serve cities better than frameworks with low penetration.
- **Take a balanced co-benefits approach.** Win-win narratives that ignore trade-offs undermine long-term legitimacy. Non-monetisable co-benefits conditionality in public investment frameworks is needed to make equity a structural requirement rather than a political promise.

THE URBAN CLIMATE GOVERNANCE SYSTEM: AMBITIOUS FRAMEWORKS, FRAGMENTED PRACTICE

Cities engaged in urban climate governance operate within a complex, overlapping system of transnational networks, strategic planning tools, impact frameworks, data platforms, and reporting systems. Three major system actors—C40, the Global Covenant of Mayors (GCoM), and NetZeroCities (NZC)—each bring tools linked to distinct impact frameworks, all feeding into the shared Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP)-ICLEI Track

reporting platform (see Figure 1). The system's ambition masks a structural problem: at the framework level, each network has defined metrics, but with multiple or competing definitions; as co-benefits flow from frameworks into city strategies, into the shared reporting system, and toward operationalisation in local data platforms, most fall away—inconsistently defined, selectively reported, and rarely measured.

Figure 1. Key Elements of the Urban Climate Action Data System. Own Illustration.

The NZC impact framework is the most recent: with 8 required (direct GHG emissions) and 79 recommended (indirect impacts/co-benefits) (NetZeroCities, 2025b). C40 operates 149 impact indicators across its monitoring, evaluation, and reporting resources (C40 and Ramboll, 2017; C40, 2019, 2020a, 2020b). GCoM has contributed a set of 9 Energy Access and Poverty Pillar (EAPP) indicators. CDP, as the shared reporting system, aims to consolidate this complexity into a single survey to reduce cities' reporting burden while

increasing transparency. This is valuable given many cities are active in multiple initiatives at once: the 2023 NetZeroCities data (CDP and ICLEI, 2023b) shows 40 of the 48 cities participate in five or more, and bespoke reporting for each would be unmanageable. While a coherent intent, a challenge is that the CDP system bridging them has remained, for co-benefits, a list of names rather than a set of standardised measures: co-benefits are identified and named, but often not quantified, or tracked. Figure 2 shows data system overlaps.

Figure 2. Overlaps in Urban Climate Action Data System and Data Overview. Own Illustration.

THE CO-BENEFITS CASCADE: FOUR STAGES, FOUR GAPS

Terwilliger, Christie and Bhattacharyya (forthcoming, 2026) trace a cascade in which co-benefits ambition progressively narrows across four stages (shown in Figure 3). The messiness and current barriers to a holistic, coherent approach is itself informative.

An accompanying, deeper structural barrier contributing to data system fragmentation described is that there is no common language, shared methodology, or consensus on which co-benefits indicators to prioritise across C40, NZC, and CDP. Co-benefits reporting to CDP is voluntary—not required—and the MyCovenant platform used by GCoM is not open access, making system-wide research comparisons difficult and peer benchmarking inconsistent.

Figure 3. The Co-Benefits Ambition Cascade. Own Illustration.

Stage 1: Frameworks to Strategies — What Cities Actually Use

As outlined above, cities developing climate strategies are doing so in the absence of any agreed taxonomy of co-benefits indicators—navigating multiple data and reporting platform architectures with no shared methodology and under significant time and capacity pressures.

Analysis of 10 Mission cities' Climate City Contracts (CCCs) against the NZC indicator framework reveals an immediate gap between what the framework proposes and what cities actually include. Of 712 co-benefits identified across the ten cities' action plans—Cluj-Napoca, Klagenfurt, Madrid, Mannheim, Sønderborg, Stockholm, Valencia, Valladolid, Vitoria-Gasteiz, and Zaragoza, only 41% had close or exact alignment with NZC indicators. A further 50% drew upon indicators from other existing processes—like the Green City Accord—and 9% could not be mapped to any NZC indicator type. This is not unique to the frontrunner sample: it holds across the broader corpus of 92 Mission Label cities' CCCs analysed (NetZeroCities, 2025a), where most co-benefits remain at the identified or consideration level—named in strategies without being linked to defined indicators, specific units of measure, or monitoring mechanisms.

Many co-benefits cited in CCCs are activities or outputs rather than impact indicators—a pattern corroborated by NZC experts. Cities list an activity (e.g., creation of a cycling network) whereas the framework's intent is an outcome indicator (e.g., modal shift rate, air quality improvement). While

there is room to build upon cities' understanding of robust monitoring systems, this recurring pattern reflects the complexities of attributing impacts to single interventions, the difficulties of translating a general indicator framework into tailored strategies, and the operational realities that there isn't a 'one-size-fits-all' approach.

Over 50% of the 33 cities that received the Mission Label as of March 2024 referenced existing plans (such as the GCoM equivalent) as foundational to their CCCs (Palma, Gugu and Meskovic-Imsirovic, 2024)—meaning co-benefits approaches are often inherited from or layered onto prior frameworks with different architectures. A review of which indicators cities are finding useful and applying locally—including refining impact frameworks collaboratively with cities—is urgently needed. Early work on this is being undertaken through activities like tracking co-benefits associated with NZC Pilot Cities Programme projects.

Stage 2: Strategies to Reporting — Inconsistency in Both Directions

When the co-benefits included in five cities' action plans are compared with what those cities reported to CDP, the picture (shown in Figure 4) is not a simple change in frequencies. Most cities in the sample had more co-benefits recorded in CDP reporting than they had included in their plans—though the two sets were mismatched in both directions, with co-benefits included but not reported, and others reported but not in the CCCs.

Figure 4. Co-Benefits Included in CCCs vs. Reported to CDP.

Vitoria-Gasteiz is the outlier, with 376 co-benefits included in its CCC against far fewer in CDP. Stockholm and Zaragoza, at the other extreme, reported more than quadruple and double the co-benefits (respectively) to CDP that were not included in their CCCs. These patterns reflect the structural misalignment shown in Figure 5: the fields of action used by CDP are categorised differently from both C40 and NZC frameworks, making direct comparison at the level of co-benefits stages systematically difficult rather than simply incomplete.

Figure 5. Differences in C40, NZC, and CDP Mitigation Fields of Action. Own Illustration.

Additional explanations for the inconsistency include high staff turnover meaning reporting can be completed by different people from those who drafted the action plan; the frequent disconnection between action and investment planning (sometimes handled by separate teams with limited or opaque coherence between sections);

variations in city-level monitoring systems; and the complexity of cities participating in multiple initiatives simultaneously, each with different reporting requirements. These are systemic conditions rather than individual errors—and they compound the structural framework misalignment shown above.

Stage 3: What 'Reported' Actually Means — Names, Not Standardised Metrics

The most important structural point about CDP co-benefits reporting is one the headline numbers obscure: when cities report 'co-benefits realised,' they are not submitting measured outcomes (see Box 1).

Box 1. CDP 'co-benefits realised' are names, not standardised metrics.

The initial 2019 CDP co-benefits realised list—across Economic, Environmental, Public Health, Social, and Other Impacts Measured categories and expanded in 2022—has remained a list of 39 co-benefits names in the guidance and questionnaire, without associated definitions or measures. Selecting 'Improved physical health' in the survey indicates that health was considered in connection with a mitigation action—it does not report a measured health outcome. Rather than a city-level failure, it reflects the wider conditions identified above—including fragmentation, a lack of consensus on which indicators to prioritise, and methods and capacity to track them across initiatives. This makes standardisation both technically difficult and contested.

Figure 6 shows how CDP co-benefits categories correlate—and fail to correlate—with C40 and NZC indicator frameworks. Many indicators across C40 and NZC domains have no direct CDP equivalent. This means that regardless of how carefully cities document these co-benefits in strategies, there is no shared reporting pathway—the system simply has no category for them. This extends to custom or locally developed indicators used by cities.

For example, of the 20 priority co-benefit indicators (excluding those to be determined) included in Bristol's CCC (explored in [Brief 3](#)), only three are captured by the CDP system. These misalignments create barriers to reporting and raise questions regarding the consistency of co-benefit approaches and what validation and verification processes are taking place globally and locally.

Figure 6. Correlation Between C40 and NZC Impact Indicator Domains and CDP Co-Benefits Realized. Own Illustration.

Stage 4: What Is Actually Measured

Beyond what is 'reported' lies the question of what is actually tracked with specific units, methodologies, and data points. The analysis of impact indicators measured by cities in CDP Q9.1-C5 (the sub-question asking for actual impact indicators for mitigation actions) shown in [Box 2](#) reveals the endpoint of the cascade. Considering most cities in the sample have CDP A-List status—considered global leaders on climate action—this raises questions regarding scaling or replicating co-benefits approaches to less-prepared cities. Because emissions reporting is required and more standardised, it gets measured; because the rest is voluntary, inconsistently defined, and capacity-intensive, it does not.

While cities do track a wider range of impacts in internal dashboards and local monitoring systems, these efforts are marginal, contained within discrete projects, largely opaque, and don't represent a coherent, consistent approach. It is worth returning to reality that there is no one-size-fits-all approach. Diversity in framework applications reflect legitimate local differences: cities operate in distinct institutional, political, and ecological contexts, and local autonomy over co-benefits definition has real advantages. The concern is that in the absence of a minimum shared architecture, it creates uncertainty on where to focus and impedes meaningful comparison and collective learning.

Box 2. Impact indicators measured across five leading Mission cities (CDP Q9.1-C5):

Estimated emissions reductions — 61 instances (the required indicator)

- Estimated energy savings per year — 13 instances
- Estimated renewable energy generated per year — 10 instances
- Other (negative emissions) — 1 instance

All social, equity, health, biodiversity, governance, and finance co-benefits: not measured as impact indicators at the global reporting level.

A Case Study in Non-Integration: The Energy Access and Poverty Pillar

The EAPP (Energy Access and Poverty Pillar) data shows a different but equally important problem: even when more substantive reporting systems are designed into the CDP questionnaire, they can end up as parallel streams that do not reinforce each other. The 2023 CDP questionnaire (CDP and ICLEI, 2023a) incorporated GCoM EAPP indicators under Q9.1-C14 and C15—a set of nine defined quantitative indicators of energy access and poverty alleviation outcomes tied to mitigation actions. Unlike the 'co-benefits realised' drop-down, EAPP reporting involves cities selecting defined indicators and specifying if values increased or decreased, representing a more substantive level of tracking.

All five cities reported EAPP indicators. Figure 7 shows the indicator frequencies: Zaragoza reported 41, Vitoria-Gasteiz 25, Madrid 22, Mannheim 21, and Stockholm 6. The most frequently used indicators were energy consumption from renewable sources (27 instances across all cities), average yearly energy consumption per capita (21), and total energy generated from renewable sources within the local boundary (18). These are quantitative measures consistently applied across multiple cities, which is unsurprising given that of the 48 Mission cities included in the 2023 NZC reporting cycle, all but Lappeenranta are GCoM members.

Yet despite all five cities reporting EAPP indicators, only Madrid also ticked 'Reduced fuel/energy poverty' as a co-benefit realised under

Figure 7. Number of EAPP Indicators Reported to CDP.

Q9.1-C9—and only once, against 22 EAPP indicator frequencies across its mitigation actions. The other cities made no connection between the EAPP and

co-benefits realised sections. These sub-questions are handled as entirely separate reporting streams with no integration requirement between them.

Box 3. The EAPP and co-benefits realised data architectures do not speak to each other.

A city can fulfil its GCoM EAPP reporting requirement (41 EAPP indicator frequencies across Zaragoza's reported mitigation actions) while simultaneously making no connection to the 'Reduced fuel/energy poverty' co-benefits realised - Social category. This is a data governance design problem, where increasing good data in one part of the system does not automatically generate complementarities in another.

The EAPP example points toward a deeper problem beyond which specific indicators are tracked. Across architectures, social inclusion dimensions—Social - 'Increased social inclusion, equality, and justice' in CDP, 'Inclusivity & Civil Society' in C40, and 'Social Inclusion, Innovation, Democracy & Cultural Impact' in NZC—are not designed to speak to each other. They sit as parallel categories with different definitions and metrics and currently no shared logic connecting them with the EAPP. A city that reports EAPP indicators may not be formally tracking democratic participation co-benefits.

Across the five Mission cities, 'Increased energy security' was in the top three co-benefits realised (behind air quality and jobs), with only Mannheim reporting 'Increased social inclusion, equality, and justice' and 'Increased access to energy.' This indicates the increased importance of energy security for cities while revealing a lack of systemic architecture for understanding how social inclusion enables better climate outcomes, where interventions generate synergies, or where they impose trade-offs on different communities. This equally reveals a gap between descriptive data and causal intelligence.

The Legitimacy Cost of Win-Win Narratives

The cascade and energy poverty data example point to a deeper problem than data gaps: cities that have led with a win-win co-benefits story face a legitimacy exposure when the trade-offs that story obscured eventually surface. Superficially reporting that renewable energy generation has improved and more citizens have been included in a governance process does not reveal whether or how those citizens helped shape which communities benefited from the renewable investment, the costs fell equitably, or the process built genuine influence over future decisions. Without a causal logic linking social and climate outcomes—and without that logic being tested against the lived experience of communities—the data remain isolated, synergies go unrealised, and

trade-offs remain hidden. This is not simply a technical measurement problem; it is a governance legitimacy problem. If citizens are not genuinely involved in defining what 'success' looks like—including the painful compromises that net zero transitions inevitably require—then the consensus governance systems are designed to build is at best shallow and at worst illusory. The GCoM's framing of 'co-benefits, trade-offs, and synergies' is more analytically honest than a purely positive co-benefits narrative precisely for this reason. Genuinely participatory co-benefits governance—the theories-of-change function described in the next section—is not just a values commitment; it is a precondition for the long-term viability of the wider transition agenda.

WHY THE CASCADE PERSISTS: A SYSTEM-LEVEL DIAGNOSIS

The Finance Gap and the Pull Toward Monetisation

The vast scale of the urban climate finance gap is most powerful driver. The EU Cities Mission Capital Hub estimates €310 billion for the 100 Mission cities to reach net zero by 2030 (BwB, 2025); UK Climate Change Committee estimates £108 billion for national net zero by 2050 (UK CCC, 2025); and the CDP's 2024 snapshot cites \$4.5 trillion annually to reach global net zero by 2050 (CCFLA, 2024; CDP, 2025). Public finance available via existing and potential policies covers only 10–35% of what is needed—the rest is expected to come from the private sector. This consensus has collectively driven cities and support networks like NZC to emphasise the subset of co-benefits that can be quantified in monetary terms: return on investment, cost savings, and energy efficiency gains. The NZC NetZeroPlanner is a decision-support tool that

illustrates recent thinking on the socioeconomic case for climate action: designed to help cities build an economic investment case for their CCC, it focuses on the seven monetisable co-benefits shown in Figure 8 (NetZeroCities, 2024, p. 7). For the model to show net zero investments generating a positive return, monetised co-benefits in economic growth and health are essential. Inclusivity co-benefits are not included. CDP frames its reporting imperative as transparency 'to deliver data that the market needs.' These framings are not wrong—mobilising private capital requires investor-legible evidence—but they systematically marginalise co-benefits that cannot be expressed in those terms, creating a market-alignment pull that progressively narrows co-benefits approaches, moving away from the inclusive, holistic innovation envisioned.

Figure 8. NetZeroPlanner Economic Model: Fields of Action & Co-Benefits.

Governance Fragmentation: Voluntary Reporting and Differing Framings and Methodologies

Cities operating under severe capacity and financial pressure will prioritise required indicators and focus on those most quantifiable in economic terms, because they carry the least institutional friction, have the most political feasibility, and the clearest investor imperative. Without a shared methodology and definitions agreed across C40, NZC, and GCoM, and without consensus on which co-benefits matter most, cities make individual choices producing incomparable data. This is not a failure of individual cities—it is the predictable result of voluntary, uncoordinated reporting across a fragmented system with multiple data platforms and architectures. A more deliberative approach requires understanding

the interdependent relationships between local actions aiming to generate co-benefits, identifying synergies, and addressing the potential barriers and trade-offs (unintended consequences, co-harms) of climate actions (Dale et al., 2020). The considerable barriers cities face to deliver integrated net zero strategies that also achieve broader sustainability goals (or enable win-wins) are essentially a collaborative governance challenge: to collectively realise co-benefits while addressing wicked, crosscutting problems like climate change (Newell, Dale and Roseland, 2018). These barriers are described as the three S's shown in [Box 4](#) below.

Box 4. The Three S's: Structural Barriers Cities Cannot Solve Alone. (Dale et al., 2020)

- 1) **Silos** - separation between researchers, private, and public sectors;
- 2) **Solitudes** - the cleavages that result in divisions between actors/groups (e.g., jargon, culture, and even geographical divides); and,
- 3) **Stovepipes** - disciplinary structures and government departments.

Together, these explain why even better-resourced Mission cities struggle to connect co-benefits across departments, frameworks, and reporting cycles—a problem of system design, not city performance.

Implementation Barriers Across the System

Analysis of barriers across 64 Mission cities and 362 Cities Mission applicants (NetZeroCities, 2022) identifies insufficient administrative and operational capacity as a primary constraint: skills to design and implement climate-related policies across sectors; capacity to carry out participatory processes; and internal infrastructure to collect reliable co-benefits data. These constraints in part explain why CCC co-benefits are often activities rather than indicators; CCC sections completed by different teams often lack coherence; and cities and support experts alike face challenges making links between learning in

monitoring systems and strategic refinements more explicit (NetZeroCities, 2025c). For most cities, co-benefits approaches remain aspirational: the capacity conditions, methods, and institutional processes for realising them are still emerging. EU Cities Mission thought leaders highlighted that CCCs are only good if they are implementable and fundable (NetZeroCities, 2025d), stressing the need for further project-to-portfolio development support and an increase in cities' responsibility without commensurate increases in staff or resources.

TOWARDS MORE TRANSFORMATIVE URBAN GOVERNANCE: THE FOUR FUNCTIONS

Taken together, these findings raise a wider question: to what depth, and toward what ends, are impact frameworks actually penetrating urban governance practices and routines? Even cities with advanced action plans struggle with the 3S's above. If leading cities—those with the most resources, expertise, and political commitment—are inconsistently connecting co-benefits across strategies, reporting systems, and monitoring routines, the implications for less-prepared cities are significant. More fundamentally, it calls into question the commitment across all governance levels to the robust monitoring systems needed to track the wider co-benefits of the energy transition—those foundational to a socially-steered, more just transition.

Despite the cascade, cities are not passive. The NZF study identifies four distinct functions (given below) through which co-benefits are used as governance tools—each with different logics, implications, and risks of misuse. The path toward more transformative urban governance requires not just adding indicators to existing frameworks, but redesigning the incentive structures, monitoring requirements, and accountability systems that shape cities' governance

choices. In short, achieving net zero or climate neutrality in cities requires advancing inclusive and holistic co-benefits approaches embodied in C40 and NZC frameworks' design: collective intelligence approaches (diverse insights not narrow metrics), with participatory feedback loops. These must be adequately resourced to break down institutional fragmentation and realise transformation in practice.

The Four Functions Model: Co-Benefits in Urban Climate Governance

- **1. Co-Benefits as Compliance.** Considered conceptually as a means of compliance to maximise efficiency of public spend where possible and meet minimum “do no significant harm” criteria (after projects are designed).
- **2. Co-Benefits as Economies of Scale.** Quantified/monetised in connection with a portfolio of solutions using innovative finance vehicles and integrated/blended business models to achieve scale and balance less profitable solutions with profitable ones.
- **3. Co-Benefits as Theories of Change.** Used as a means of developing a shared understanding of particular challenges/problems and engender buy-in/ownership of goals, identify/prioritise solutions, and define “success” in achieving desired change.
- **4. Co-Benefits as Advocacy & Communications.** Used in dialogue to generate policy attention for solutions as well as communicate the imperative to act and demonstrate the impact of policy solutions to citizens to build momentum or political space for acceleration.

The functions are not mutually exclusive—cities draw on more than one simultaneously—but they are not equally available. **Function 1** is the minimum default: necessary but insufficient. **Function 2** is essential for capital mobilisation but risks a market-based transition determined by the best-resourced actors. **Function 3** is the most crowded out by finance and

capacity pressures—and the most vital for long-term legitimacy and a just transition. **Function 4** has the most widening potential but vulnerable to cherry-picked co-benefits while equity dimensions remain invisible. The finance gap systematically pushes cities toward Functions 1 and 2. [Figure 9](#) maps the governance risks and transformational gains of each.

Figure 9. The Four Functions: Drivers, Governance Risks & Transformational Gains. Own illustration.

Making the socioeconomic case for urban climate action rests heavily on the political promise of co-benefits—in cities across the globe. If those co-benefits remain poorly tracked, weakly demonstrated, and governed through business-as-usual functions alone, city leaders and the national climate neutrality agendas they are working toward carry growing reputational and legitimacy risks.

In the UK and EU, these risks have largely been framed through win-win narratives in which multistakeholder, multisectoral project portfolios—lucrative and higher risk, lower return alike—are assembled for co-investment toward a net zero market. This appears to widen governance: more actors beyond the city are involved. But the widening is structurally narrow—defined by large-scale economic metrics, keystone investors, and the stakeholders best-positioned to hold decision-making power—and disconnected from participatory

theories of change. Coordination costs and impact infrastructure remain with city departments; corporate actors gain positioning without proportionate co-investment in the governance systems that would make the portfolio genuinely collective. The result risks a false dichotomy: conceptual deliberation with citizens on one side, large-scale net zero market forces on the other—overpromising and underdelivering the impact that communities actually need (see Cossey and Acquier, 2026, on deceptive vs. robust win-wins).

The Four Functions Model offers a practical governance audit for reducing those risks. The difference between stalled, partial, or eroded progress and truly transformational net zero futures depends on whether cities, networks, and decision-makers at all levels of policy-making can genuinely shift the balance—deliberately, with resources—from closed, market-driven to more open systems.

KEY INSIGHTS & POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

For Policymakers and Funders

- Invest in understanding how the co-benefits functions operate at all levels of governance. The evidence base on how cities actually use co-benefits—and which internal monitoring systems and hybrid impact frameworks developed to track them—is thin. Building that evidence base, and making non-monetisable co-benefits a condition of investment models rather than an optional reporting choice, are prerequisites for more holistic, socially-rooted net zero pathways: equity outcomes require structural embedding, not political promise.
- Establish a minimum set of required co-benefits indicators—particularly social, equity, and governance process outcomes—to enable comparability and accountability. **Brief 1's** REPAIR framework provides an analytical starting point for governance process indicators. See Ayllón and Jenkins (2026) for work on just transition metrics.
- Advance interoperability standards across initiatives and platforms at the level of co-benefits. Competing taxonomies, platform architectures like CDP and MyCovenant, and the need to balance city-level customisation with shared minimum standards remain unresolved. A jointly maintained minimum co-benefits taxonomy—accounting for the EU and UK taxonomies—would build collective evidence without multiplying city burden. This could start with supporting cities to connect energy security and energy access and poverty outcomes with other co-benefits, with a focus on co-impacts and trade-offs across fields of action.

For Mission-Minded Cities and Practitioners

- Audit co-benefits approaches against the Four Functions Model. If formal functions dominate, regulatory and finance needs are being addressed while legitimacy and equity risks accumulate. Identify which functions are absent and what governance investments would move towards transformational functions.
- Distinguish between co-benefits named, co-benefits indicated, and co-benefits measured in strategic documents. For each co-benefit cited, ask which of these three levels it represents. Prioritise five to ten most central to the theory of change and build monitoring systems to consistently track them.

- Design cross-departmental co-benefits monitoring from the outset. Establish shared monitoring ownership across action planning, investment planning, and reporting teams for strategic update cycles.

For Governance Networks

- Commission a systematic review of which framework indicators cities are actually finding useful and applying locally. The gap between NZC indicators proposed and city uptake reflects a mismatch between framework design and practical operability. Framework co-refinement would serve cities better than comprehensive frameworks with low penetration.
- Build shared capacity-building on co-benefits measurement methodology. The tools and methods for tracking social, equity, and governance process co-benefits are in early stages of development. Dedicated guidance, peer learning exchange, and capacity-building support specifically for participatory co-benefits approaches is urgently needed.
- Develop guidance on co-risks alongside co-benefits. The GCoM framing of 'co-benefits, trade-offs, and synergies' is more analytically honest than CDP's predominantly positive framing. Supporting cities to engage with distributional impacts and trade-offs is essential for building genuine legitimacy.

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What's Next in the Series

This is **Brief 2** of the NZF Series, summarising the doctoral thesis of Joel Terwilliger: **Towards More Participatory Net Zero Futures (2022-2026)**. The next titles in the series are: (**Brief 3**) Governing a Just Net Zero Transition: The Bristol Toolkit and City and Community Visions for Change; (**Brief 4**) Governing Net Zero Missions: Innovation, Alignment, and Mobilisation Insights from Bristol and Fellow Cities; and (**Brief 5**) Missions, Myths, and Contemporary Procedural Governance Tools: Reflections and a Proposed Research Agenda.

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